

PSYCHOLOGICAL TESTS AND PARADIGMS TO ENHANCE SKILLS IN SPORT: AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

Introduction: Psychological tests and paradigms are frequently used for the preparation of athletes in the field of high-performance sports. Although there is little debate over the importance of psychological testing in sports, some disagreement exists in the sport psychology literature over the best tests for athletes. **Objective:** Examine the scientific literature and identify the main psychological tests used to help improve the performance of collegiate athletes. **Methods:** A descriptive integrative review-type study was performed. Scientific articles were accessed in the electronic databases: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), Pubmed and PsycINFO, Google Scholar, and Researchgate. **Results and Discussion:** The electronic search retrieved $\sum n = 352$ studies. After applying search filters and removing duplicates, 112 studies were obtained. After classification by consulting the abstract and reading it completely to match the eligibility criteria, 7 final studies were obtained. A new search was performed in the Google Scholar and ResearchGate repositories, adding 3 studies. Thus, for the final analysis, $\sum n = 10$ studies were obtained. For a final analysis, the tests identified allowed for an integrative view of the different types of psychological tests adopted in the sporting context. **Conclusion:** Results indicate that different tests can be used as a complement for the training of high-performance athletes.

Keywords: sports; psychology; neuroscience; performance; athletes.

INTRODUCTION

The identification of an optimal psychologic state for high-performance sport, and more importantly, the ability to train the mind for that state, has been the goal of sport psychology researchers for over 30 years (HAMMERMEISTER; VONGUENTHNER, 2005). As a result, psychological tests and paradigms are frequently used for the preparation of athletes in the field of high-performance sports. Psychological assessment can be defined as a scientific and professional activity that consists of collecting, integrating, and analyzing data about a specific individual (CID et al., 2022). Although there is little debate over the importance of psychological testing in sports, some disagreement exists in the sport psychology literature over the best tests for athletes.

OBJECTIVE

The purpose of this review was to systematically examine the scientific literature and identify the main psychological tests used to help improve the performance of collegiate athletes.

METHODS

A descriptive integrative review type study was performed, allowing completed studies to be analyzed and conclusions to be reached on the topic of interest by analyzing significant studies for Evidence-Based Practice and collaborating to deepen knowledge and applicability.

Sources

Scientific articles on the subject were accessed in the following electronic databases: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), Pubmed and PsycINFO. Additionally, to identify possible additional studies, Google Scholar and Researchgate repositories were used. The following descriptors were used, in English, in accordance with the Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS) and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH): “athlete”, “sport”, “psychology”, “motivation” and “test”.

Data Collect

Data collection followed the following sequence:

- a) Exploratory reading of all pre-selected material;
- b) Selective reading;
- c) Registration of relevant information from the sources consulted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The electronic search retrieved 210 studies (SciELO), 101 studies (PubMed/MEDLINE) and n = 41 studies (PSycINFO), totaling $\sum n = 352$ studies. After applying search filters and removing duplicates, 112 studies were obtained. After classification by consulting the abstract and reading it completely to match the eligibility criteria, 7 final studies were obtained. A new search was performed in the Google Scholar and ResearchGate repositories, adding 3 studies. Thus, for the final analysis, $\sum n = 10$ studies were obtained. A flowchart is presented in Figure 1, and a summary of the final findings is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1— Flowchart.

Source: Authors (2023).

Table 1— Summary of the final findings

Authors	Year	Test / Paradigm
LIMA <i>et al.</i>	2022	Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test and Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2R
FIOCHI-MARQUES; MELO-SILVA; OLIVEIRA	2022	Academic and Athletic Identity Scale, Professional Identity Scale and Flourishing Scale
BARREIRA <i>et al.</i>	2022	Sport Motivation Scale-II
GUERRERO; FERNANDES	2021	Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 and Sport Competition Anxiety Test
SILVA <i>et al.</i>	2019	Sports Orientation Questionnaire
HERNANDEZ; VOSER	2019	Flow State Scale-2
HERNANDEZ; VOSER	2012	Leadership Scale for Sports
ROHLFS <i>et al.</i>	2008	Brunel Mood Scale
GONÇALVES; BELO	2007	Sport Competition Anxiety Trait
MACHADO; BANDEIRA; PAWLOWSKI	2013	Psychological Well-being Scale

Source: Authors (2023).

The main objective of this work was to identify the main psychological tests used to help improve the performance of college athletes. For a final analysis, results from 10 scientific studies published in specialized journals were categorized. The tests identified in these studies were tabulated, which allowed an integrative view of the different types of psychological tests adopted in the sporting context.

CONCLUSION

Results indicate that different tests can be used as a complement for the training of high-performance athletes. However, in future research, this study should be complemented by an analysis of the specificities of each test or paradigm.

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